

Framework for Rapid Prediction of Fire-Induced Heat Flux on Concrete Tunnel Liners with Curved Ceilings

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ABSTRACT

Recent vehicular fires in concrete-lined tunnels have demonstrated the vulnerability of the liner to heat-induced spalling and cracking damage. To evaluate the structural fire resistance of either existing or newly designed tunnel structures, there is a need for fast-running tools that can accurately predict the distribution and severity of fire-induced heat exposure over the interior surface of the liner. This study proposes an analytical prediction framework which is more realistic than current design fire curves and yet less computationally intensive than high-fidelity numerical solutions. The Confined Discretized Solid Flame (CDSF) model is proposed for calculating the spatial contour of total heat flux imparted to the tunnel liner due to an enclosed fire. The CDSF computation includes both radiation heat transfer via a 3D discretized solid flame and a convective region representing the ceiling jet of smoke and hot gas. CDSF heat flux results show strong agreement with experimentally validated computational models at a fraction of the computational cost over a matrix of four large vehicle fire sizes and three tunnel prototypes with curved ceilings (i.e. horseshoe or circular cross-sections). The fast-running CDSF approach is conducive to parametric thermal analysis and stochastic damage evaluation for concrete tunnel liners exposed to fire.

Keywords: tunnel; fire; concrete; heat flux; radiation; convection; solid flame model; FDS analysis

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20 1. INTRODUCTION

21 Tunnels are vitally important to the transportation of goods and people by providing efficient passage
22 through difficult terrain and under waterways and urban areas. Fires due to vehicular accidents, especially
23 those involving flammable cargo, pose one of the most significant hazards to tunnel safety. The first and
24 foremost objective during a tunnel fire event is to achieve egress and preserve life safety of the occupants
25 and first responders. Modern tunnel design practices typically use ventilation systems to remove vehicular
26 exhaust during normal operations, and these systems can also be used to disperse smoke from a fire event
27 inside the tunnel. Smoke management during a fire event has been studied at length and is addressed in
28 numerous design standards worldwide [1,2].

29 The subsequent objective is to preserve tunnel functionality and mitigate fire-induced damage to these
30 critical infrastructure assets. Flame energy and hot gases generated by vehicular fires in the confined tunnel
31 environment have the potential to induce severe damage to the tunnel structure. Repairs and concurrent
32 loss of tunnel functionality due to closure can lead to significant economic losses. For example, a severe
33 fire from a 2008 cargo train accident inside the Channel Tunnel between the UK and France inflicted
34 significant damage over a 750-m length of the concrete tunnel lining [3]. According to the technical
35 investigation of that event, the concrete liner spalled to various depths and breached through the section at
36 some locations, which ultimately led to a reduction of the structure's load bearing capacity and increased
37 the risk of progressive collapse. The fire event was followed by 5 months of repair at an estimated cost of
38 \$70 million (in 2008 US dollars). Also, a 1991 heavy goods vehicle (HGV) fire within the Mont Blanc
39 Tunnel connecting France and Italy [4] and a tanker truck fire in the Caldecott Tunnel between Oakland
40 and Orinda in California, USA [5] resulted in multiple casualties and structural damage that required several
41 months of repair.

42 To evaluate the resilience of tunnel structures to fire-induced damage, engineers must first estimate the
43 heat transfer from the fire to the tunnel liner. There are generally three types of fire models that are used
44 to evaluate structures for thermal exposure: (1) parametric standard fire curves, (2) computational fluid

45 dynamics (CFD) models, and (3) semi-empirical models of varying complexity. In practice, a parametric
46 fire curve is often used for its simplicity by representing the fire as a temperature time history, which can
47 be applied directly to the exposed surface of nearby structural elements. Significant experimental work over
48 the past few decades has generated temperature time histories for potential types and sizes of fire in tunnels
49 [6,7] – in particular, the Rijkswaterstaat (RWS) time-temperature curve [8] is one of the most widely
50 adopted standards worldwide. In the US, the National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) defines fire
51 protection performance criteria for tunnels based on the RWS curve [1], which characterizes the fire event
52 as an upper-bound temperature time history due to combustion of a 50-m³ fuel tanker with a heat release
53 rate (HRR) of 300 MW and duration of 120 min. The temperature of the RWS curve rapidly increases to
54 1200°C in 10 minutes from ignition and remains above that temperature for 2 hours [1]. Though the RWS
55 and other similar fire curves are straightforward to apply, they do not consider the spatial distribution of
56 heat exposure due to a concentrated fire and can result in inaccurate assessments.

57 Using a specified temperature time history simplistically avoids the calculation of realistic heat transfer
58 from the fire to the liner via flame radiation and convection from smoke and hot gases. For a more robust
59 solution, CFD analyses can provide high-resolution, data-rich calculations of the magnitude and spatial
60 distribution of fire demands within a tunnel. However, these models are computationally intensive and
61 require a wide array of input parameters, including meshing, detailed material characteristics, and
62 combustion parameters such as soot yield and radiation transport. If experimental data or design guidance
63 are not available to select these parameters, then reasonable assumptions must be made based on previous
64 precedent or good practice. The CFD approach is not feasible for rapid assessment of an inventory of tunnels
65 or for a wide range of fire scenarios, nor is it practical for a stochastic assessment of tunnel fire resilience
66 with realistic variability of the material, geotechnical, and/or fire characteristics.

67 As a third option, various semi-empirical fire models based on test results as well as first principles
68 have been developed to predict the heat transfer from flames, smoke, and hot gas to nearby targets. These
69 alternative approaches to CFD or simplified fire curves represent a so-called “intermediate” class of model

70 complexity that can conservatively calculate the spatial distribution of fire effects with moderate
71 computational effort. For a fire in an enclosed tunnel environment, an intermediate approach must address
72 both the flame radiation and convective effects from the combustion byproducts.

73 The simplest approach for radiative heat flux prediction is a point source model [9], which uses a single
74 radiation-emitting point located at the tridimensional center of the fire to emit energy via radiation to nearby
75 targets. With a modest increase in complexity, solid flame models [9] represent the fire as a vertical 3D
76 solid (typically a cylinder) which radiates to targets using an average emissive power and pre-calculated
77 view factors. To better account for smoke generated during combustion, the 3D fire object can be bifurcated
78 into a lower luminous zone (i.e. the unobstructed flame layer) and an upper smoke layer to obtain a
79 “modified” solid flame model. To improve the radiation resolution at reduced standoff, the solid flame
80 surfaces can be discretized to calculate radiation as a summation of total exposure [10] – the “view” of the
81 target from the discretized solid flame is therefore flexible for any orientation or standoff. Open-air (i.e.
82 unconfined) vehicle and/or cargo fires can be represented primarily as sources of intense flame radiation
83 for which the solid flame or other radiation emitting models can be appropriately selected. For example, a
84 modified discretized solid flame (MDSF) model has been used previously to calculate heat transfer from
85 open-air fires to steel-supported bridges [11]. Solid flame models are also used extensively to calculate safe
86 distance separation between fuel storage tanks and neighboring structures due to potentially severe
87 hydrocarbon pool fires [12].

88 Intermediate calculations that account for convective effects include zone modeling packages (such as
89 OZone [13] and CFAST [14]) and empirical relationships have been developed for compartment fires in
90 buildings [15]. These models can conservatively calculate spatial and temporal temperature fields due to
91 smoke and gas buildup as well as ceiling layering and corner/wall effects for an enclosed room fire. To
92 date, a few of these convection-focused semi-empirical models have been adapted for a tunnel fire scenario
93 [16–18]. However, zone models may struggle to adequately capture the larger amounts of flame radiation
94 associated with severe tunnel fires.

95 To appropriately model a severe fire in a tunnel environment, the solid flame and zone model concepts
96 can be merged to calculate the total heat energy due to flame radiation, smoke effects, and convection from
97 hot gaseous combustion byproducts. This paper proposes an intermediate fire model called the confined
98 discretized solid flame (CDSF) model for rapid and reliable predictions of the total heat flux (radiation and
99 convection) imparted to tunnel liners from a range of typical vehicle fires. The CDSF model is calibrated
100 via comparison to CFD solutions that have been developed in NIST's Fire Dynamics Simulator (FDS) [19]
101 and validated against three large-scale tunnel fire tests. As a first iteration, the CDSF model currently
102 neglects the effects of forced ventilation or longitudinal slope as a simplification – the influence of these
103 parameters on the distribution of fire effects will be considered in future phases of this project. A
104 commercial 3D computer-aided design software, Rhino [20], and the accompanying visual programming
105 language, Grasshopper [21], are used to implement the CDSF model for their extended capabilities in
106 complex, parametric geometric analysis and visualization. The predicted spatial distribution of total heat
107 flux from the CDSF model can be used to directly evaluate the thermomechanical response of the tunnel
108 liner, particularly for spalling, concrete weakening, and expansion-induced stress effects. The
109 computational efficiency of the CDSF model versus its CFD counterparts can enable stochastic assessment
110 of numerous input parameters over an inventory of tunnels or for a range of fire scenarios.

111 **2. CONFINED DISCRETIZED SOLID FLAME (CDSF) MODEL**

112 The CDSF is a hybrid analytical model that includes both radiative and convective effects for
113 calculating the total incident heat flux on the interior surface of a tunnel liner due to an enclosed fire. Similar
114 to the previously proposed MDSF models for large open-air fires [11], the flames are represented as a solid
115 3D object whose surfaces are discretized and assigned an emissive power. As shown in Figure 1 (left), each
116 target surface on the tunnel liner receives straight-line radiation from each discretized solid flame element
117 in accordance with their relative emissivity, standoff, and angles of orientation. When developing the solid
118 flame model, the flame height is initially generated without consideration of tunnel confinement using semi-
119 empirical equations for open-air fires [22]. If the calculated “free flame” height extends beyond the tunnel

120 ceiling, the flame shape is compressed and becomes “confined” by the tunnel – the result is regarded as the
 121 confined flame shape. Radiative energy conservation is considered for the flame confinement. A convective
 122 region is then defined along the tunnel ceiling to account for thermal demands from ceiling jets of smoke
 123 and hot gas (Figure 1, right). Each target surface on the liner receives convective heat flux in accordance
 124 with its location within the convective region. The summation of radiative and convective effects, illustrated
 125 below in Figure 1, represents the total fire-induced heat flux experienced by the interior face of the tunnel
 126 liner mesh.

127
 128 *Figure 1 Illustrations of radiative (left) and convective (right) heat transfer for the CDSF model*

129 **2.1 Modeling Assumptions**

130 Two simplifications are made regarding the tunnel prototypes for this first phase of CDSF model
 131 development. First, the tunnels are assumed to have no longitudinal grade to obtain a symmetric
 132 distribution of fire effects in both longitudinal directions. Future work will include the effects of the tunnel
 133 grade on the longitudinal movement of the smoke and hot gases. Second, all fire scenarios in this paper are
 134 evaluated assuming natural (i.e. unforced) ventilation in the tunnel during the fire event. Though many
 135 tunnels are designed with forced ventilation systems along their ceilings, their fans, ducts, and electrical
 136 power may be disrupted, damaged, or ineffective during a severe fire. If it remains operational, the
 137 ventilation system can move the combustion byproducts and alter the resulting distribution of convective
 138 heat flux, as well as the progression of combustion due to increased air flow. The next phase of development
 139 for the CDSF model will incorporate the effects of realistic ranges of ventilation volume and velocity.

140 For this first phase of CDSF model development, the fire location is assumed to be at the longitudinal
141 and transverse center of the tunnel to enforce symmetry and neglect the increased air inflow and ventilation
142 when the opening is close to the fire. Different longitudinal and transverse fire locations relative to the
143 tunnel liner and openings will be explored in future work. The longitudinal distance from the tunnel
144 openings to the fire may influence airflow during the fire, potentially affecting the HRR and resulting heat
145 transfer to the liner. If the fire is located in an off-center transverse location, the standoff to the liner will
146 be less on one side and generate a localized increase in radiation heat flux.

147 **2.2 Solid Flame Geometry**

148 Severe fires in tunnels are typically generated from fuels that include vehicles (cars, buses, trucks, train
149 cars, locomotives, etc.) and the cargo they carry (the most severe being hydrocarbons and flammable
150 consumer or industrial products). This study focuses on severe fires due to buses and heavy goods vehicles
151 (HGV's), which are identified in NFPA 502 as typical design fire scenarios for tunnels [1]. Empirical
152 estimates of HRR for a range of bus and HGV fires is available in the published literature. Fires due to
153 these vehicles and their cargo will have an elongated, approximately rectangular footprint that resembles
154 the actual vehicle dimensions, as illustrated in Figure 2 for an HGV. These fires would realistically involve
155 an eclectic mix of burning materials such as hydrocarbon fuel, lubricants, plastics, foams, wood, batteries,
156 electronics, etc. Estimating the aggregate combustion properties of these materials, which would be needed
157 to calculate the geometry and intensity of the resulting fire, is difficult due to limited availability of key
158 data such as mass loss rate and heat of combustion.

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Figure 2 Development of the CDSF footprint based on an HGV fire scenario

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Rather than explicitly modeling the aggregate combustion of the various materials, the vehicle fire scenarios in this study are represented more simplistically as hydrocarbon pool fires with equivalent HRR. Semi-empirical predictions of the intensity and geometry of hydrocarbon pool fires are well established from decades of previous research, and combustion properties for these fuels are readily available in the published literature. This approach is analogous to the use of equivalent weights of TNT as a measure of explosive energy when evaluating blast effects on structures [23]. In this study, the equivalent footprint of a diesel pool fire is used to provide the same energy release as an actual vehicle and/or cargo fire. Diesel is chosen as the fuel type because the experimental data used for model validation (shown later in this paper) was generated from fire tests performed with diesel [7]. The rectangular footprint of the equivalent diesel pool fire (see Figure 2) is scaled from the vehicle footprint to obtain the same HRR as the pre-defined vehicle fire scenario. Further research is needed to demonstrate the equivalence of exposure to an idealized diesel fire versus a realistic fire involving a combination of vehicles and cargo, particularly regarding mass loss rate, soot yield, and radiative fraction.

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In the existing literature, almost all semi-empirical expressions for calculating hydrocarbon pool fire characteristics (including HRR [24], radiative fraction [12,25], and flame height [15]) are based on experiments performed with circular pool footprints. The characteristics of a solid flame model with a non-circular footprint can be obtained by calculating an effective circular fire diameter, $D_{f,eff}$ (m), based on the

178 area of the non-circular footprint. For a rectangular fire footprint with length L_f (m) and width W_f (m), $D_{f,eff}$
 179 is calculated as follows:

$$180 \quad D_{f,eff} = \sqrt{\frac{4(L_f \cdot W_f)}{\pi}} \quad (1)$$

181 $D_{f,eff}$ can then be used as input for semi-empirical calculations of HRR and flame height that assume a
 182 circular pool fire footprint. Previous literature has indicated that $D_{f,eff}$ can be calculated directly from the
 183 full area ($A_f = L_f \cdot W_f$) of rectangular footprints that have an aspect ratio (i.e. ratio of longer edge length to
 184 shorter edge length) less than 2.5 [12]. For this study, the equivalent diesel pool fire footprint as shown in
 185 Figure 2 is conservatively set to an aspect ratio of 2.

186 Peak HRR, $\dot{Q}_{f,max}$ (kW), for the rectangular pool fire is calculated using $D_{f,eff}$ [24]:

$$187 \quad \dot{Q}_{f,max} = \dot{m}'' \Delta H_{c,eff} A_f (1 - e^{-k\beta \cdot D_{f,eff}}) \quad (2)$$

188 where \dot{m}'' is the mass loss rate per unit area (kg/(m²-s)), $\Delta H_{c,eff}$ is the effective heat of combustion (kJ/kg),
 189 and $k\beta$ is an empirical constant (m⁻¹). These variables are fuel specific and can be obtained from available
 190 references [26]. The free flame height, H_f (m), is calculated as a function of $\dot{Q}_{f,max}$ (kW) and $D_{f,eff}$ [15]:

$$H_f = 0.235 \dot{Q}_{f,max}^{0.4} - 1.02 D_{f,eff} \quad (3)$$

191 If the free flame height is less than the ceiling height, then the 3D solid flame could be simply extruded
 192 as a rectangular box with height H_f [11]. An extruded rectangular shape, however, can produce “blind
 193 spots” when calculating the radiation heat flux to a nearby target from the corners of the solid flame.
 194 Specifically, steep angles between the normal vectors of the target surfaces and those of the discretized fire
 195 surfaces at the corners can artificially decrease the calculated radiation when compared to a realistic fire.
 196 To mitigate corner effects, the “analytical” footprint for the CDSF model in Figure 2 is approximated as an
 197 ellipse with the same perimeter (and thus the same overall radiation emission) as the equivalent diesel fire’s

198 rectangular footprint. The ratio of major axis to minor axis for the analytical elliptical footprint is the same
199 as the aspect ratio of the equivalent diesel pool footprint, which equals 2.0.

200 Figure 3 shows that the free flame is vertically bifurcated into a main body (which is vertically extruded
201 from the elliptical footprint over the lower $0.4H_f$) and a tapering top section (which approximates the flaring
202 or whirling nature of the flames over the upper $0.6H_f$) per previous research by Zhou et al. [27]. To again
203 avoid sharp transitions in the CDSF's shape, the conical shape proposed by Zhou et al. [27] is replaced with
204 a truncated ellipsoid dome as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 3.

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Figure 3 Schematic comparison of the free flame and confined flame models in the tunnel cross-section

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2.3 Radiation Heat Transfer

209 The emissive power, E (kW/m²), of the flames is assumed to be uniform across the surface of the 3D
 210 free flame shape and is calculated as a function of $\dot{Q}_{f,max}$ (kW); total free flame surface area, A (m²); and
 211 radiative fraction, χ_r (i.e. the fraction of the energy released from the fire as thermal radiation [12,25]):

$$E = \frac{\chi_r \dot{Q}_{f,max}}{A} \quad (4)$$

212 Values of χ_r are readily available in the current literature on hydrocarbon pool fires, either as a general
 213 expression for common fuel types [12] or specific to individual fuels based on experimental testing [25]. In
 214 this study, χ_r for diesel is calculated according to Munoz et al. [25] as a function of the fire's effective
 215 diameter:

$$\chi_{rad} = \begin{cases} \text{for } D_{f,eff} \leq 5\text{m}: & 0.158D_{f,eff}^{0.15} \\ \text{for } D_{f,eff} > 5\text{m}: & 0.436D_{f,eff}^{-0.58} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

216 As shown in Figure 3, the height of the fire's base above the road surface, H_{base} (m), approximately
 217 accounts for the bumper height of the burning vehicle. If H_f plus H_{base} remains below the tunnel height
 218 (Figure 3a), then H_f is used as the “analytical” flame height, $H_{f,analytical}$ (m), for CDSF modeling. However,
 219 the free flame height from Eq. 3 will often exceed the height of the tunnel, H_T (m), for significant fires. In
 220 those cases, the free flame height is reduced to fit inside the tunnel enclosure, thus “confined”, to obtain
 221 $H_{f,analytical}$. The confined flame height, H_c , (m) is therefore calculated as follows:

$$H_c = H_T - 0.02H_f - H_{base} \quad (6)$$

222 To provide the flame surfaces with adequate view of the tunnel liner at close range (i.e. to “engulf” those
 223 targets with appropriately high radiation heat flux), the top of the ellipsoid dome is offset from the tunnel
 224 ceiling by a small value equaling $0.02H_f$.

225 For free flame heights that just exceed the tunnel height (Figure 3b), the dome is compressed while
 226 the height of the extruded ellipse body remains at $0.4H_f$. For increasingly severe fires (Figure 3c), the free

227 flame height can become so tall that the ellipsoid dome would be unrealistically compressed or even
 228 eliminated (resulting in poor analytical calculations of radiation heat flux on the ceiling) if no height
 229 adjustments were made to the $0.4H_f$ main body. To preserve the bifurcated structure of the confined solid
 230 flame, the height of the confined flame body is modeled as no greater than $0.75H_c$, and the ellipsoid dome
 231 can therefore be no less than $0.25H_c$. The confined flame shape will naturally have less surface area than
 232 the free flame shape; however, since the HRR output is unchanged, both the free flame and confined flame
 233 shapes should emit the same total radiation from their discretized surfaces. The emissive power in the
 234 ellipsoid dome, $E_d(\text{kW}/\text{m}^2)$, of the confined flame is therefore increased from the free flame emissivity, E ,
 235 from Eq. 4 by the ratios shown below to account for engulfment of the ceiling:

$$236 \quad E_d = E \left(\frac{A_d}{A_d'} \right) \left(\frac{A_b}{A_b'} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

237 A_b and A_d (m^2) are the surface areas of the free flame body and dome, and A_b' and A_d' (m^2) are the surface
 238 areas of the confined flame body and dome. The ratio of A_d to A_d' will be greater than unity for any confined
 239 flame shape. The ratio of A_b to A_b' will be greater than unity only if the free flame body height exceeds
 240 $0.75H_c$. This second ratio is squared in Eq. 7 to account for the increasing flame turbulence when the free
 241 flame height is much higher than the tunnel height. The emissive power in the ellipsoid body remains at the
 242 free flame emissivity from Eq. 4 ($E_b = E$). As will be demonstrated later in this paper, predictions of
 243 radiation heat fluxes from this approach to energy conservation compare well with validated high-fidelity
 244 FDS solutions for a wide range of fire severities.

245 Having defined the analytical flame shape and surface emissive power, the radiative heat flux received
 246 on the visible surfaces of the tunnel liner can be calculated as follows:

$$q''_{rad,j} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i F_{i \rightarrow j} = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i \frac{A_i \cos \theta_i \cos \theta_j}{\pi r_{i \rightarrow j}^2} \quad (8)$$

247 The radiative contribution from each emitting flame surface, i , is summed at each target surface, j . Total
 248 radiation heat flux at each target surface, $q''_{rad,j}$, is calculated as a function of the flame surface emissive
 249 power, E_i (kW), and the dimensionless view factor, $F_{i \rightarrow j}$, between receiving and emitting surfaces.

250 2.4 Convective Heat Transfer

251 A convective region at the tunnel ceiling is included in the CDSF to simulate the heat flux contributed
 252 by the ceiling jet and smoke effects. Through FDS-informed calibration (which will be demonstrated later
 253 in this paper), convective heat flux is applied to target elements within the predefined convective zone,
 254 which has a vertical depth D_{cz} (m) along the total length of the tunnel (see Figure 1). The value of D_{cz} is
 255 based on the luminous flame fraction, χ_{lum} (i.e. the luminous height of a pool fire flame that is unobstructed
 256 by smoke [25]). Values of χ_{lum} for a diesel pool fire can be calculated as a function of $D_{f,eff}$ per previous
 257 experimental work by Munoz et al. [25]:

$$\chi_{lum} = \begin{cases} \text{for } D_{f,eff} < 5m: & 0.3 \\ \text{for } 5m \leq D_{f,eff} < 20m: & 1.26D_{f,eff}^{-0.2577} - 0.533 \\ \text{for } D_{f,eff} \geq 20m: & 0.05 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

258 The analytical flame height $H_{f,analytical}$ (equal to H_f for unconfined flame shapes and H_c for confined
 259 shapes) is thereby multiplied by χ_{lum} to obtain the depth of the convective zone:

$$D_{cz} = H_T - H_{base} - \chi_{lum}H_{f,analytical} \quad (10)$$

260 Previous studies of tunnel fires have shown strong correlation between the spatial distributions of
 261 convective heat flux and ceiling jet gas temperature. For example, Li and Ingason [28] developed an
 262 exponential scaling fit for longitudinal temperature distribution within the smoke region based on model-
 263 scale tunnel fire tests. Using an FDS-informed fit that is correlated to peak HRR and tunnel size, the authors
 264 have developed a similar model for the longitudinal decay of convective heat flux under the tunnel ceiling,
 265 beginning with the calculation of the maximum convective heat flux directly above the fire:

$$q_{c,max} = 68 \ln(\dot{Q}_{f,max}) - 702 \quad (11)$$

266 The longitudinal decay of q_c (kW/m²) away from the fire location is calculated via Eq. 12, where x (m)
 267 represents the longitudinal distance from the fire's center:

$$\frac{q_c(x)}{q_{c,max}} = 0.38e^{-6.75\left(\frac{x-x_v}{H_T}\right)} + 0.5e^{-0.27\left(\frac{x-x_v}{H_T}\right)} \quad (12)$$

268 The “virtual origin” of the fire, x_v , (m) is a function of the flame length, L_{flame} , (m) and the height of the
 269 tunnel, H_T [28]:

$$x_v = \begin{cases} \text{for } L_{flame} > 5.2H_T: L_{flame} - 5.2H_T \\ \text{for } L_{flame} \leq 5.2H_T: 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$L_{flame} = 12H_T\dot{Q}_f^* \quad (14)$$

270 Dimensionless HRR ratio, \dot{Q}_f^* , is calculated via Eq. 15 as a function of peak HRR, $\dot{Q}_{f,max}$ (kW); air density,
 271 ρ_0 (kg/m³); air heat capacity, c_p (kJ/kg-K); ambient air temperature, T_0 (K); gravitational constant, g (m/s²);
 272 the tunnel opening area, A_o (m²); and effective tunnel height H_{ef} (m) (equal to H_T minus H_{base}):

$$\dot{Q}_f^* = \frac{\dot{Q}_{f,max}}{\rho_0 c_p T_0 g^{\frac{1}{2}} A_o H_{ef}^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (15)$$

273 Previous research by Rafiei [29] on rectangular tunnels examined the relationship between transverse
 274 and longitudinal movement of the smoke along the ceiling as a function of its buoyancy. Based on that
 275 study, the convective heat flux in the CDSF model decreases linearly along the radial length of the ceiling
 276 from $q_c(x)$ at H_T to zero at the bottom of the convective region (i.e. at a height of H_T minus D_{cz}).

277 By combining the radiative and convective effects, the spatial distribution of total incident heat flux
 278 can be mapped to the discretized tunnel liner. A detailed flowchart which illustrate steps for both radiation
 279 and convection computation in the proposed model is shown in Figure 4. An example distribution for a
 280 large fire in a circular tunnel is shown in Figure 5. Later sections of this paper will show good comparisons
 281 of heat flux predictions between the CDSF model and experimentally validated FDS solutions.

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Figure 4 Flowchart of the proposed CDSF framework

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285 *Figure 5 Section cut at the longitudinal center showing typical CDSF output (heat flux values in kW/m²)*286 **3. COMPUTATIONAL MODEL VALIDATION**

287 Given the current literature, direct experimental validation of total heat flux is not feasible since most
 288 full-scale fire tests in tunnels to date have focused on temperature distributions, combustion dynamics, and
 289 smoke movement. Temperature data from a full-scale tunnel fire test program in the Memorial Tunnel in
 290 West Virginia, USA [7] and heat flux data from the fire test program in the Runehamar Tunnel in Norway
 291 [30] are used for FDS model validation [19]. A mesh sensitivity study was conducted for the Memorial
 292 Tunnel fire tests, and the resulting mesh zone distribution was then used for both validation cases. The
 293 validated FDS modeling approach is subsequently used to develop several benchmark fire scenarios within
 294 a selection of tunnel cross-sections that are typical of the current US inventory. When adapting the FDS
 295 model for these tunnel fire scenarios, the meshing approach, combustion modeling parameters, and material
 296 inputs are kept consistent with the validation cases. Total heat flux results from those FDS simulations are
 297 then used to computationally calibrate the CDSF approach in the next section of this paper.

298 **3.1 Modeling the Memorial Tunnel Fire Tests**

299 The Memorial Tunnel, decommissioned in 1987, has a horseshoe-shaped cross-section with a width of
 300 8.77 m, maximum height of 7.87 m, total length of 854 m, and a longitudinal grade of 3.2% [7]. The tunnel

301 was subjected to controlled fire events located 617 m from the north portal. Two tests from the Memorial
302 Tunnel program that were conducted without forced ventilation (Nos. 501 and 502) are used in this study
303 for FDS validation. The tests had target HRR of 20 MW and 50 MW and used diesel in rectangular pans as
304 the fire source, which was located in the transverse center of the tunnel section. The fire source was modeled
305 in FDS as a rectangular burner surface whose area and heat release rate per unit area (HRRPUA) were
306 defined to achieve the same HRR as that recorded during the tests. Soot yield is taken as 0.1 for diesel [26],
307 and the fire's radiative fraction is calculated per Eq. 5 as a function of the effective diameter of the fire [25].
308 Default FDS parameters for radiation simulation, such as the number of solid angles (100 angles) and the
309 application of the gray gas radiation transport solver, were implemented for all analysis cases.

310 A layered surface with thickness of 0.3 m (the same thickness as the actual tunnel liner) was used to
311 model the tunnel liner surfaces with concrete material properties per default settings in accordance with
312 NIST online resources for FDS [19]. The slope of the tunnel was applied by specifying gravity components
313 in FDS. The fuel pans and road surfaces were defined as inert. Tunnel openings were modeled using open
314 vents, beyond which the ambient environment is assumed to exist. These boundary conditions allow
315 longitudinal air movement across the opening through the length of the tunnel during the fire.

316 Both the gas temperature and total heat flux were measured longitudinally along the crest of the tunnel
317 ceiling in FDS. Temperature measurements in the test were taken at several time increments using
318 thermocouple trees at 15 cross-sections throughout the length of the tunnel with expected measurement
319 accuracy of 0.75%. Gas temperature data was provided in the test report as contour lines in 37.8°C (100°F)
320 increments – comparisons with FDS were made by linearly interpolating across those contours. The time
321 history of the FDS gas temperatures just below the ceiling were measured at the same locations reported
322 from the fire tests as well as at a denser spacing directly above the fire. Time-dependent heat flux was
323 measured at increments ranging from 2 m to 5 m, again with more measurements taken near the fire.

324 The interior volume of the tunnel is discretized into approximate cubic cells – for improved
325 computational efficiency, the mesh is finest near the location of the fire and then increasingly coarse toward

326 the ends of the tunnel. A mesh sensitivity study was performed for the larger 50 MW fire to determine an
 327 adequate size of the finest mesh at the fire location as well as an appropriate mesh zone distribution along
 328 the tunnel length. Mesh selection is based on good agreement with the Memorial Tunnel fire test data as
 329 well as solution convergence. In a separate study, McGrattan et al. [31] also used FDS to model the
 330 Memorial Tunnel fire tests and adopted a 0.30-m cubic mesh over a length of 130 m centered on the fire
 331 location (with coarser mesh beyond). In this study, the finest mesh size is similarly set to 0.25 m and applied
 332 over lengths of either 30 m, 60 m, or 100 m centered on the fire location, as shown in Figure 6. This figure
 333 also shows that the mesh size is doubled over a 100-m length beyond the finest mesh zone and then doubled
 334 again for the remaining tunnel length.

335
 336 *Figure 6 Mesh distributions for the FDS sensitivity study in the Memorial Tunnel*

337 Figure 7a shows that FDS results from all three mesh variations agree well with the experimentally
 338 measured ceiling temperatures. The plot also shows that the temperature distribution is negligibly sensitive
 339 to changes in mesh size distribution. Figure 7b shows noticeable yet relatively small mesh sensitivity for
 340 total heat flux at the ceiling. In particular, each model experiences a small jump in heat flux at the transitions
 341 between mesh sizes. To reduce the influence of turbulence in the FDS time history results, note that the gas
 342 temperature from FDS at 3 min was the time-average of temperature data in the 10 second interval at 3 min
 343 \pm 5 seconds. The FDS heat flux is the average heat flux during the steady state. Since the heat flux reduces
 344 to less than 50 kW/m² within \pm 25m for the 50 MW fire scenario, mesh option (b) (with the finest mesh
 345 at \pm 30 m from the fire) experiences a less significant heat flux jump than option (a) and is more
 346 computationally efficient than option (c). Mesh option (b) is therefore selected for the remaining FDS

347 analyses in this study. Using this meshing approach, the FDS ceiling temperatures show good agreement
 348 with the corresponding test results for both the 50 MW and 20 MW fire scenarios (see Figure 8). The same
 349 10-second time averaging is used for temperatures in the 20 MW scenario at the 5 min mark.

350
 351 *Figure 7 Comparison of ceiling measurements for the 50 MW Memorial Tunnel fire: (a) gas temperature after 3 min*
 352 *elapsed time (test [7] vs. FDS), and (b) average steady state heat flux (FDS only)*

353
 354 *Figure 8 Comparison of FDS ceiling temperature (meshing option (b)) and test data [7] for the 20 MW and 50 MW*
 355 *Memorial Tunnel fires*

356 Due to its complexity and computational cost, FDS analysis may be impractical for conventional design
 357 or stochastic parametric analysis, which requires a less demanding tool to accurately predict thermal
 358 demands due to tunnel fires. For the same analysis of the 50 MW Memorial Tunnel fire test, the CDSF
 359 approach (resulting in heat flux data similar to that shown in Figure 5) required only 0.5% of the
 360 computational runtime for an analysis with 200-second fire duration (which adequately achieves steady
 361 state) compared to FDS 6 (run with parallel processing and full system dedication).

362 **3.2 Modeling the Runehammar Tunnel Fire Tests**

363 The decommissioned Runehammar Tunnel has an approximate rectangular cross-section with a width of
 364 9 m, height of 6 m, and total length of 1600 m with variable longitudinal grade. The fire source was located
 365 at the transverse center and about 1037 m from the east portal in a location with 1% grade [30]. To shield
 366 personnel and the tunnel liner from the fire effects, a steel frame portal with fire protection boards on its
 367 interior face was erected around the fire location. Mobile fan units placed near the east portal generated an
 368 average longitudinal velocity ranging from 2.0 m/s to 2.5 m/s during all tests. Heat flux data was measured
 369 at longitudinally at 0 m, 10 m, 20 m and 40 m downstream from the fire center along the ceiling of the fire
 370 protection boards. Since it shared the same fuel as the proposed approach, a 6 MW diesel fire test from this
 371 test program is selected for validation of the model in FDS with respect to ceiling heat flux.

372 The fire source for the Runehamar Tunnel fire test was modeled as a rectangular burner surface, similar
 373 to that used for the Memorial Tunnel fire tests. The height of the burner surface was assumed to be 0.5m
 374 from the ground. Parameters for the reaction such as soot yield and radiative fraction were selected to be
 375 consistent with the validation analyses of the Memorial Tunnel fire tests. Modeling parameters such as the
 376 material properties and open boundary condition at the tunnel opening is also the same as that used to model
 377 the Memorial Tunnel fire tests. Initial wind velocity from the east portal of the tunnel was taken to be 2.1
 378 m/s. As in the test, the model included the fire protection boards, with the geometry and material properties
 379 from the test report [30], that were placed around the fire source. The steel frame was not modeled in FDS
 380 due to a lack of specific information. Incident heat fluxes on the ceiling were measure in FDS at the same
 381 location as in the test.

382 Figure 9 shows the comparison of heat flux time history measurement between the 6 MW diesel pool
 383 fire test in Runehamar Tunnel and the FDS results. Right above the fire at 0 m, the FDS heat flux time
 384 history is conservatively consistent with the steady state heat flux from the test. The FDS simulation does
 385 not capture the initial spike in heat flux as the fire ramps up around ~1 min; however, the duration of the
 386 spike is short and therefore not structurally significant. At 10m, 20m and 40m, the FDS heat flux shows
 387 overall good agreement with the test results, with differences less than 1 kW/m².

388

389 *Figure 9 Heat release rate and ceiling heat flux time histories for the 6 MW Runehamar Tunnel fire*

390 4. PARAMETRIC STUDY

391 The proposed CDSF model and experimentally validated FDS approach are subsequently used to
 392 evaluate the total heat flux distribution on the interior face of the tunnel liner for a wider matrix of fire
 393 scenarios and tunnel cross-section shapes and sizes. In each FDS analysis, the HRR is modeled with an
 394 initial 30-second parabolic t^2 ramp-up and then maintained at steady state. For all fire scenarios considered
 395 in this study, a total FDS time history of 5 minutes is sufficient to develop steady state heat flux exposure
 396 to the liner. Heat flux measurements in the CDSF model are taken at every liner discretization as illustrated
 397 in Figure 10. Heat flux time histories are recorded in the FDS model at discrete points in the longitudinal
 398 direction (at the ceiling and along the sidewall) as well as radially around the fire location. These points
 399 correspond to the centers of select liner discretization in the CDSF model.

400
401

Figure 10 Locations of heat flux measurement to compare the CDSF and FDS models

402 4.1 Tunnel Prototypes

403 According to current data [32], four cross-sectional shapes are typically used for the majority of the
 404 current tunnel inventory in the US: horseshoe, rectangular, circular, and oval. The accumulated inventory
 405 from 1882 to 2015 for each tunnel shape is plotted in Figure 11. The data clearly shows that cross-sections
 406 with curved ceilings are the most common. It is interesting to note that some tunnels with curved structural
 407 ceilings are identified in the inventory database as rectangular due to the installation of flat false ceilings
 408 (such as the Fort Pitt Tunnel [33]) which separate the traffic passageway from the ventilation conduit. The
 409 CDSF model proposed in this paper is developed for tunnels with curved ceilings in order to address the
 410 largest segment of the current inventory. Future work will adapt the CDSF model for rectangular shapes,
 411 which pose additional modeling challenges due to lower clearance and cornering effects on the movement
 412 of smoke and gas, which lead to increasingly turbulent combustion results.

413

414

Figure 11 Accumulated number and length of tunnels from 1882 to 2015 [32]

415 Figure 12 shows the cross-sections of the three tunnel prototypes that are used to demonstrate the CDSF
416 model in this paper. Per the current limitations of the CDSF approach, all tunnel prototypes are assumed to
417 be naturally ventilated with no longitudinal grade. As was shown in Figure 11, the horseshoe shape is by
418 far the most common in US practice. Due to the technological development of tunnel boring machines
419 (TBM's) [34], the segmented circular cross-section is predicted to be an increasingly common tunnel shape
420 and is therefore highlighted in this study. Prototype (A) has similar dimensions as the aforementioned
421 Memorial Tunnel [7]. Prototype (B) has the same shape and proportions as (A) but has a larger section area.
422 Prototype (C) is a circular cross-section whose base is cross-cut by the roadway surface. The section area
423 of (B) and (C) are the same. Figure 13 shows that the widths of these prototypes are typical compared to
424 circular and horseshoe tunnels currently in the US inventory [32].

425
426
427

Figure 12 Cross-sectional dimensions (in meters) for the horseshoe, larger horseshoe, and circular tunnel prototypes

Figure 13 Tunnel roadway width frequency for circular and horseshoe tunnel shapes [32]

428
429

4.2 Fire Scenarios

431 Design fires for transportation infrastructure are typically defined in terms of HRR and based on the
 432 calorific value and size of the fuel source [35]. For example, NFPA 502 [1] specifies 20MW-30MW as the
 433 peak HRR for bus fires and 70MW-200MW for HGVs. Four fire scenarios are selected for this study with
 434 HRR values that are representative of these vehicles: 30MW, 70MW, 100MW, and 200MW [1,35]. Figure
 435 14 shows the actual vehicle footprint (dashed gray lines) given by AASHTO [36] for the bus and HGV. As
 436 discussed earlier in this paper, these footprints are converted to an equivalent diesel pool footprint that is
 437 modeled via CDSF and FDS. To maximize flame height for the specified HRR of each vehicle, an
 438 equivalent hydrocarbon pool footprint was developed with an aspect ratio of 2 and a pool fire area A_f that
 439 satisfies Eq. 2 for diesel. These equivalent rectangular footprints are shown with gray solid lines in Figure
 440 14 for the four fire scenarios. An elliptical base with the same perimeter as the equivalent rectangular
 441 footprint is shown in red in Figure 14. As discussed previously, the elliptical footprints are used in the
 442 CDSF model to avoid the errors in target view factor that can occur near the corners of a boxy solid flame

443 shape. In contrast, the FDS results are negligibly sensitive to the rectangular vs. elliptical shape of the pool
 444 fire footprint. The rectangular footprints are therefore directly implemented in the FDS simulations due to
 445 their easier implementation.

446
 447 *Figure 14 Dimensions (in meters) of the actual vehicle footprint (dashed gray), equivalent diesel pool footprint*
 448 *(solid gray) for FDS, and equivalent elliptical footprint (solid red) for CDSF*

449 Table 1 summarizes the matrix of fire scenarios that are considered for each tunnel prototype. The 200
 450 MW fire is not considered for the smaller horseshoe tunnel since its width is slightly smaller than that of
 451 the equivalent diesel elliptical footprint for that fire (i.e. the width of the CDSF solid flame shape won't fit
 452 in this tunnel). Future work will explore alterations in the footprint geometry such that very large fires can
 453 be confined within smaller tunnel openings. For this paper, however, the CDSF approach is kept consistent
 454 with the elliptical footprint and solid flame approach described in Section 2.

455 *Table 1 Matrix for comparative parametric analyses in FDS and CDSF*

		TUNNEL PROTOTYPES		
		A. Smaller Horseshoe	B. Larger Horseshoe	C. Circular
FIRE SCENARIOS	B-1 (30MW)	Yes	Yes	Yes
	HGV-1 (70MW)	Yes	Yes	Yes
	HGV-2 (100MW)	Yes	Yes	Yes
	HGV-3 (200MW)	No	Yes	Yes

456 Preliminary analyses of the CDSF were performed to determine a sufficient resolution of flame surface
457 discretization to achieve solution convergence. The 200MW scenario had the largest solid flame dimensions
458 and comfortably achieved convergence with 54 elements around the elliptical perimeter, 10 elements over
459 the body height, and 50 elements over the dome height. The same discretization pattern was used for the
460 smaller fires, though a coarser mesh could be tailored to a smaller flame height and fire footprint.

461 5. COMPARISON AND DISCUSSION

462 Heat flux results from the CDSF and FDS models are compared at the locations marked with black
463 dots in Figure 10 along the ceiling, sidewall, and cross-section. The CDSF output predicts the steady state
464 total heat flux at each target location, while FDS provides a heat flux time history at the selected
465 measurement points. For example, FDS time histories of total heat flux on the ceiling directly above the
466 fire are plotted in Figure 15 for all four fire scenarios in Tunnel B. Results for all fire scenarios show
467 oscillation about a steady state mean value, with the 200 MW fire showing the largest relative fluctuation.
468 The statistical mean value of the steady state heat flux (after $t = 30$ seconds) is plotted along with upper and
469 lower bounds representing +/- one standard deviation. All statistical values are plotted as time histories
470 with an initial 30-second t^2 ramp-up to the steady state heat flux [35]:

$$q''(t) = \begin{cases} \text{for } t < 30 \text{ sec:} & q''_{max} \cdot \left(\frac{t}{30}\right)^2 \\ \text{for } t \geq 30 \text{ sec:} & q''_{max} \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

471
472 *Figure 15 Total heat flux time histories at the ceiling of Tunnel B directly above each fire*

473 When considering thermal exposure to tunnel occupants in the event of a tunnel fire, it may be
 474 appropriate to consider peak values. However, the temperature increase in the concrete liner is governed by
 475 the cumulative fire exposure. Temperature gradients that develop through the liner thickness will
 476 characterize the structural response of the concrete via spalling, weakening, and restraint of thermal
 477 expansion [37]. The sensitivity of the development of these gradients is examined by comparing thermal
 478 analyses of the tunnel liner thickness for four heat flux exposure time histories from FDS: the mean, the
 479 upper and lower bounds (i.e. +/- one standard deviation), and the complete time history. The 63-cm liner
 480 thickness (see Figure 12) is equally discretized into 100 layers for 1D heat flow analysis, which is performed

481 using SAFIR [38]. The concrete is assumed to be normal weight, with a density of 2300 kg/m^3 and moisture
482 content of 46 kg/m^3 . The concrete material type in SAFIR is defined as SILCONC_EN (i.e. normal-weight
483 siliceous concrete), and the thermal properties are assumed according to Eurocode 2 [39]. For each analysis,
484 the heat flux time history is applied on one “exposed” face of the concrete panel, and the time histories of
485 temperature gradient development are calculated. All time histories are analyzed with a constant 0.2-second
486 time step, which is sufficiently small based on preliminary calculations and smaller than the minimum time
487 step from the full FDS results. Ambient temperature is applied as a thermal boundary condition to the
488 unheated face, which is assigned a relative emissivity of 0.5 and a convective coefficient of 4 kW/m^2 [39].

489 Figure 16 plots the temperature gradients that develop through the panel thickness after 5 minutes of
490 exposure to the heat flux time histories from Figure 15. The gradient due to the mean heat flux curves shows
491 very close agreement with those developed from the full FDS time history. For the HGV-3, the gradients
492 due to the upper and lower bounds have little variation from the mean exposure. The CDSF is therefore
493 calibrated to predict heat flux values between the upper and lower bound for this fire. For the other three
494 fires, the difference in gradient between the lower bound and mean heat flux is larger than that between the
495 mean and upper bound. Based on these results, the CDSF model is calibrated to target heat flux predictions
496 for the B-1, HGV-1, and HGV-2 fires that fall between the mean and upper bound FDS values.

497
498 *Figure 16 Comparison of thru-thickness temperature gradients at the ceiling of Tunnel B directly above each fire*

499 Figure 17 compares the FDS and CDSF steady state heat fluxes at the locations in Figure 10 for the
500 HGV-2 fire in all three prototype tunnels. The region between the upper and lower bound FDS solutions is
501 shaded in red and the mean value is shown as a black solid line. The presence of a strong ceiling jet (i.e.
502 where the heat flux distribution has a “bump”) at the ceiling is exhibited by the FDS results and also
503 captured by the CDSF model. The plots show good overall consistency between the CDSF results and the
504 mean value of the FDS results. The CDSF model not only provides an accurate prediction of the maximum
505 heat flux at the fire location but also shows good consistency with FDS for the decay of heat exposure
506 longitudinally and transversely.

507
508

Figure 17 Comparison of steady-state heat flux predicted by FDS and CDSF for fire scenario HGV-2

509 Similarly good agreement for all fire scenarios and tunnel prototypes is demonstrated by comparing
 510 two values of root mean square error (*RMSE*): (1) between the CDSF results and the FDS mean ($RMSE_{CDSF}$),
 511 and (2) between the FDS upper/lower bound and the FDS mean ($RMSE_{BOUND}$). If the $RMSE_{CDSF}$ is smaller
 512 than $RMSE_{BOUND}$, then the discrepancy of the CDSF results from the FDS results is within the range defined
 513 by the standard deviation. The *RMSE*'s are calculated via Eqs. 17 and 18, in which n is the device number
 514 and N is the total number of devices for each set of measurements. For the longitudinal comparisons (ceiling
 515 and side wall), heat flux data measured around fire location is weighted more heavily due to the denser
 516 locations of devices.

$$RMSE_{CDSF} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (q''_{n,CDSF} - q''_{n,FDSMEAN})^2}{N}} \quad (17)$$

$$RMSE_{BOUND} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{n=1}^N (q''_{n,FDSBOUND} - q''_{n,FDSMEAN})^2}{N}} \quad (18)$$

517 Figure 18 compares the *RMSE* for all tunnel prototypes and fire scenarios. Figure 18b shows that the
 518 *RMSE*'s for all side wall measurements are less than 5 kW/m², demonstrating good relative agreement
 519 between the CDSF and FDS results. For the ceiling and radial cross-sectional measurements in Figure 18a
 520 and c, the variation between CDSF and FDS mean values are larger than for the side wall but generally
 521 remain within one standard deviation of the FDS mean value. The exceptions are for HGV-1 and HGV-2
 522 in Tunnel B, where $RMSE_{CDSF}$ for the radial cross-sectional measurement (Figure 18c) is up to 12 kW/m²
 523 greater than the corresponding $RMSE_{BOUND}$. Despite this, cross-section plots of these heat fluxes in Figure
 524 19 show that the CDSF results are almost all conservatively larger than the FDS mean, especially at the
 525 locations of higher heat flux. All other tunnel prototypes and fire scenarios show similarly conservative
 526 comparisons for radial cross-sectional heat fluxes.

527
528

Figure 18 Comparison of $RMSE_{CDSF}$ and $RMSE_{BOUND}$ for all fire scenarios and tunnel prototypes

529
530

Figure 19 Comparison of radial cross-section heat fluxes for HGV-1 and HGV-2 in Tunnel B

531 Figure 18a shows that the longitudinal heat fluxes along the ceiling have even lower *RSME* than the
532 radial cross-sectional measurements. Figure 20 plots the raw error between the CDSF longitudinal ceiling
533 heat flux and the FDS mean to demonstrate that these values meet the aforementioned calibration
534 objectives. The circles represent the raw error (CDSF minus FDS mean) at every x location from the fire
535 location up to 60-m away (again, assuming symmetric fire effects due to natural ventilation and zero grade).
536 The dashed lines represent the upper and lower bounds (\pm one standard deviation) from the mean FDS
537 heat fluxes – these values converge to near-zero as the FDS results become significantly less turbulent at
538 locations further from the fire. Per the calibration objective, the CDSF predictions for HGV-3 in Tunnels
539 B and C are bracketed between the FDS lower and upper bounds. CDSF predictions for the other three fire
540 scenarios are also bounded by their target range between the FDS mean and upper bound with one
541 exception. The HGV-2 fire in Tunnel A follows the lower bound beyond a distance of ~ 8 m from the fire's
542 center; however, predictions near the fire (where the liner response will be most severe) are closer to the
543 FDS mean and meet the calibration objective.

544

545

Figure 20 Comparison of raw error from the FDS mean for the longitudinal ceiling heat flux

546 6. CONCLUSIONS

547 This paper proposes a confined discretized solid flame (CDSF) approach for rapid calculation of the
 548 total heat flux on concrete tunnel liners due to vehicular fire events. The CDSF model utilizes semi-
 549 empirical models and first principles to calculate (1) radiation heat flux via a discretized solid flame model
 550 and (2) convective heat flux from smoke and hot gases. Three tunnel prototypes that are typical of the US
 551 tunnel inventory were used to develop the CDSF approach versus validated computational models. Natural
 552 ventilation and zero slope were assumed for the tunnel prototypes. An equivalent diesel pool fire was used
 553 as a simplified representation of complex vehicular fires with the same heat release rate (HRR). The
 554 equivalence was developed from the relationship between the target HRR and the effective diameter of the
 555 pool fire.

556 High-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) solutions were experimentally validated using
557 available data from previous full-scale tunnel fire tests. The validated CFD approach was implemented to
558 model the prototype tunnels and fire scenarios as a baseline for calibrating the CDSF framework. Heat flux
559 time histories from the CFD solutions were statistically analysed and used for 1D heat flow analysis of the
560 concrete liner. To conservatively calculate the temperature increase of the liner, a bounding envelope of
561 steady state heat flux was established for each fire scenario to realistically account for the turbulence in the
562 CFD solutions. These envelopes were used as calibration targets to verify the accuracy of the proposed
563 CDSF framework.

564 The proposed CDSF framework demonstrated good agreement with the FDS results across the matrix
565 of tunnel prototypes and fire sizes. The CDSF model predicts total incident heat fluxes on concrete tunnel
566 liners with curved ceilings at a fraction of the computational effort needed for high-fidelity CFD solutions.
567 The heat flux distributions produced by the CDSF model can be used as input for evaluating fire-induced
568 spalling, the effects of restrained thermal expansion, permanent concrete deterioration, and other damage
569 to non-structural components inside the tunnel. The proposed framework has significant potential for rapid
570 post-fire evaluation of tunnels and for stochastic assessment of the risk of fire-induced damage and loss of
571 functionality.

572 In its first iteration, the CDSF model cannot yet accommodate the effects of forced ventilation or
573 longitudinal slope. The current CDSF model is simplified to predict a symmetric longitudinal and transverse
574 distribution of fire effects for a zero-slope tunnel with natural ventilation. The current model assumes that
575 the fire location is at the transverse center of the tunnel and has adequate longitudinal distance from the
576 opening. Open boundary conditions were implemented at the openings of the high-fidelity FDS models that
577 were used to calibrate the CDSF model; however, the influence of the openings at close proximity to the
578 fire has not yet been validated in the CDSF model. Future phases of this project will add capabilities to
579 CDSF to account for an increased range of realistic tunnel characteristics, particularly forced ventilation,
580 slope, and proximity to openings.

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